

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: The article deals with the effectiveness of artificial intelligence in industrial enterprises. Artificial intelligence makes it possible to improve the quality of products of industrial enterprises.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, production process, enterprise safety level, quality control, equipment condition analysis, robotic arm, enterprise costs.

The industry has become one of the main areas for the adoption of products and solutions using artificial intelligence - and in the coming years it may become the main one.

Artificial intelligence can be applied at the production level to improve business processes and coordinate (orchestrate) various production systems. The use of intelligent assistants helps to reduce human errors, simplify the production process and reduce downtime during process changeovers. Image recognition functions can analyze the movements of employees and moving equipment, thereby increasing the level of security in the enterprise, and are also used for quality control and analysis of the condition of equipment. In industry, systems based on artificial intelligence are developing rapidly. Meticulous MarketResearch predicts this segment will grow by 39% in 2030, and the industrial AI market will reach \$27 billion by 2027.

The leader in the use of these products is the United States, followed by the countries of Southeast Asia (most of the manufacturing enterprises are located in China). However, globally, the figure is quite modest - only 6% of industrial organizations in the world, according to Gartner, use artificial intelligence.

Factories and plants use artificial intelligence to control product output and quality, to control robots and smart machines, track stocks of raw materials in warehouses, optimize logistics, and many other tasks. The main task of artificial intelligence in factories is "accounting and control".

Artificial intelligence is better than people at analyzing this data, so it moves from observation and accounting to the next stage - recommendatory and predictive products based on artificial intelligence are becoming more and more popular. Here are recent examples:

In May 2022, the Chinese Synergies raised \$12 million to create a personal "assistant" who will give factory managers advice and recommendations on organizing production, purchasing raw materials, changing product lines, and so

on. Now there are many companies in the world offering AI solutions to plants and factories that allow them to control not only production and warehouses, but also the work of employees. With better goals - as a rule, AI should monitor work safety, help reduce the number of injuries and prevent accidents.

In May 2022, San Francisco-based startup Voxel raised \$15 million, which, using computer vision technology, monitors workers in factories and factories in real time, including whether they are wearing overalls, whether there are helmets on their heads, whether they are all safety regulations for handling mechanisms and so on. So, Toyota signed an agreement with Texas-based Invisible AI to develop a "vision platform" that connects to surveillance cameras or sensors. Invisible AI promises that the platform will allow not only to monitor the production of cars, but also, for example, "analyze the movements of the human body, including the movements of the torso, limbs and joints, in search of alarm signals."

In other words, using the algorithms embedded in it, the platform can understand whether a person is performing actions that can cause an accident, harm himself or production. In the next two years, Invisible AI will install about 500 peripherals connected to its platform at Toyota plants in Texas.

Artificial intelligence is also being introduced to check and improve the quality of products by metallurgical enterprises. For example, in the oxygen-converter shop of the enterprise, a set of digital solutions has been developed, which are used on secondary processing units and continuous casting of steel. Technology testing has confirmed their effectiveness. A software and hardware complex is installed on the ladle furnace unit to control the metal blowing with argon. The elements of the complex are a robotic arm, cameras in a protective casing for collecting streaming video data at high temperatures, and an ensemble of mathematical models based on neural networks.

In real time, the complex is shooting and analyzing video, evaluates and issues recommendations for the steelmaker. Such a comprehensive monitoring of the production process allows you to improve product quality. AI-based software systems view, analyze data from video cameras and, if problems are detected, instantly transmit information to responsible employees.

Such a system allows to reduce downtime in production and reduce the costs of enterprises by an average of 10%. Artificial intelligence controls loading and unloading operations, monitors sensor readings, monitors errors in the operation of units and assemblies at enterprises, records the movement of

personnel and the presence of employees of the required qualifications at the site of the relevant work.

The specifics of the work of artificial intelligence in industry is due to the fact that when creating models, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of enterprises, which, even when working with the same metal, may differ from each other. But with these differences, artificial intelligence helps all industrial organizations where direct algorithmic calculation is impossible or difficult, where there are many variables and unknowns, where the engineer evaluates the necessary actions based on his own expert experience.

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